

Leadership Failure in Crisis Management: A Comparative Analytical Reading of the Models of the King and Pharaoh in the Qur'anic Narrative

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Translator's Note

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Abstract

Leadership failure in crisis management has been extensively studied in contemporary management literature, yet the Qur'anic narrative remains largely underutilised as an analytical framework for understanding this phenomenon. This study addresses that gap by conducting a systematic comparative analysis of two contrasting Qur'anic leadership models — the King in the story of Joseph (PBUH) and Pharaoh in the story of Moses (PBUH) — to identify the structural determinants of leadership success and failure in critical contexts. Drawing on a deductive qualitative method, the study applies a five-element analytical framework derived from crisis management and leadership literature: cognitive flexibility, information openness, institutional delegation, de-escalation management, and emotional intelligence. The analysis reveals that leadership failure in crisis management is fundamentally rooted in the leader's internal disposition rather than external circumstances, and that the Qur'anic narrative offers a rich and methodologically rigorous source for developing leadership models that integrate classical Islamic scholarship with contemporary management theory.

Keywords: leadership failure; crisis management; Qur'anic narrative; analytical framework; cognitive flexibility; Islamic leadership.

1. Introduction

Crises are an inseparable part of life for states and institutions; they constitute moments of genuine testing of leadership's ability to make crucial decisions under pressure and uncertainty. The danger of crises arises not only from their sudden nature but from how they are managed: under sound leadership a crisis can become an opportunity for reform and renewal, or a cause of collapse when it falls into the hands of incapable or rigid leaders. In this context, contemporary crisis management literature emphasises that leadership failure is not only related to lack of resources or weak information; it is largely linked to the leader's internal disposition — their cognitive flexibility, willingness to listen, and ability to adapt to changing variables (Boin et al., 2017; Mitroff, 2005). Hence, analysing leadership models in crisis contexts is a scientific necessity for understanding the dynamics of success and failure in management.

The Qur'ān provides a rich body of knowledge containing leadership models that confronted real crises in different historical contexts. These models go beyond the homiletic or narrative dimension; they contain analytical dimensions that can be extracted to understand leadership behaviour and crisis management. Among the most prominent are the model of the King in the story of Joseph (PBUH), who demonstrated a high capacity for listening, delegation, and strategic planning in facing a major economic crisis, and the model of Pharaoh, who embodied leadership failure through arrogance, rejection of advice, and the subordination of public interest to self-interest. Rahman (1982) pointed out that the Qur'anic narrative contains "indicative patterns" that can be employed in analysing social and leadership phenomena — an observation that opens the door to a methodical reading of these models beyond traditional exegesis.

Accordingly, this study aims to conduct a comparative analysis of the two Qur'anic models — the King and Pharaoh — in crisis management, by exploring the fundamental differences in their leadership patterns and uncovering the structural reasons behind the success of one and the failure of the other. The study adopts a deductive-analytical approach connecting the Qur'anic text to a five-element analytical framework: cognitive flexibility, information openness, institutional delegation, de-escalation management, and emotional intelligence, thereby enabling a deeper understanding of leadership failure in contemporary institutional contexts.

2. Crisis Management in the Management Literature

Crisis management is considered one of the fastest-growing and most developed management fields in recent decades, due to the increasing frequency of organisational, political, and environmental crises facing institutions and states. Boin et al. (2017, p. 5) define a crisis as "a serious threat to the basic structures of the social system that cannot be contained by routine procedures" — a definition that emphasises the structural dimension of a crisis, not merely the incidental event.

Crisis management theories have evolved along three main trajectories: first, the structural approach, which regards crises as a product of institutional dysfunction; second, the behavioural approach, which attributes crises to individual decisions and reactions; and third, the integrative approach, which combines both factors (Mitroff, 2005, p. 12). The behavioural approach is particularly relevant to this study because it places the crisis at the heart of leadership action rather than external variables.

Management literature distinguishes four sequential phases: pre-crisis (prevention and planning), acute crisis (immediate response), post-crisis (recovery), and institutional learning (Boin et al., 2017, p. 18). Leadership failure is most prevalent in the first two phases: many leaders neglect the prevention stage and subsequently err in their response once the crisis erupts.

3. Elements of Leadership Failure in Crisis Management

Based on the literature reviewed in the preceding section, an analytical framework composed of five main elements that explain leadership failure in crisis contexts can be extracted. This framework is subsequently applied to analyse the two Qur'anic models in section 6.

3.1 Cognitive Flexibility vs. Cognitive Rigidity

Cognitive flexibility refers to the leader's ability to adjust perceptions and decisions in response to new information, even when it challenges previous beliefs. Cognitive rigidity, in contrast, leads to clinging to outdated views despite accumulating evidence of their unsuitability (Hogan & Kaiser, 2005, p. 172).

3.2 Information Openness vs. Exclusion

Information openness means the leader's readiness to listen to experts and advisors and to encourage upward information flow. Exclusion means monopolising decision-making and isolating oneself from vital information sources (Rahim, 2002, p. 80).

3.3 Institutional Delegation vs. Power Centralisation

Institutional delegation is the distribution of authority according to competence, increasing the institution's effectiveness and crisis-response capacity. Power centralisation means monopolising decisions and rejecting partnership, thereby slowing response and multiplying errors (Drucker, 1954, p. 145).

3.4 De-escalation Management vs. Escalation of Commitment

De-escalation management is the leader's ability to contain a crisis in its early stages and prevent it from worsening. Escalation of commitment is the tendency to persist in a failing course of action because of prior investments, turning a small crisis into a catastrophe (Staw, 1981, p. 577).

3.5 Emotional Intelligence vs. Emotional Impulsivity

Emotional intelligence includes self-awareness, impulse control, and empathy with others. Leaders lacking these abilities are more prone to making hasty or aggressive decisions in times of crisis (Goleman, 1998, p. 94).

4. Contextual Background of the Crisis in the Two Qur'anic Models

Each model has its own historical and institutional context, and the nature of the crisis each leader faced differs entirely. Clarifying this background is necessary to understand the reasons for the King's success and Pharaoh's failure, independent of purely moral judgements.

4.1 Institutional Context and Nature of the Crisis in the King's Model

In the King's time, the Egyptian state suffered from structural weakness in its institutions, with a closed, class-based theocratic bureaucracy. However, the system retained sufficient relative flexibility to allow it to transcend class barriers in emergencies (Aljazairy, 2026a, pp. 98–103).

The crisis facing the King was an existential economic one: seven severe years of famine threatening the collapse of the state, mass migration, and possibly enemy invasion. The elite of priests and advisors failed to interpret the dream that troubled him, opening a window for a competent individual from outside the ruling class — Joseph (PBUH) — to emerge (Aljazairy, 2026a, pp. 98–100).

4.2 Institutional Context and Nature of the Crisis in Pharaoh's Model

In Pharaoh's time, the Egyptian state had transformed into a closed military-theocratic system where despotism had reached the point of deifying the ruler, emptying institutions of their substance, and making law an instrument of repression (Aljazairy, 2026a, pp. 168–170). Hornung (1999, p. 183) emphasises that the Egyptian state of that era rested on “ideological servitude” founded on the superiority of the pharaonic bloodline, making any change in the decision-making structure an existential threat to the ruler's divine legitimacy, not merely an administrative adjustment.

The crisis faced by Pharaoh was not natural or economic but a complex political and humanitarian one: the emergence of a prophet — Moses (PBUH) — calling for the liberation of the Children of Israel from slavery and challenging Pharaoh's divine legitimacy. The crisis developed in stages and included successive plagues (blood, frogs, vermin, locusts) that weakened the state economically and morally yet did not break Pharaoh's rigidity (Aljazairy, 2026a, pp. 116–117).

5. Research Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative method based on comparative deductive analysis to examine leadership failure in crisis management through two opposing Qur'anic models: the King in the story of Joseph (PBUH) and Pharaoh in the story of Moses (PBUH). The approach treats the Qur'anic text as a cognitive source capable of producing interpretive models for understanding leadership behaviour, not merely as a homiletic or historical narrative.

It should be noted that this study builds analytically on Aljazairy's (2026a) book *Leadership Between Reform and Revolution* as the foundational methodological framework for an administrative reading of Qur'anic narratives — a pioneering work that established a systematic analytical-administrative methodology not previously applied to Qur'anic narrative in Arabic specialised literature. The two papers “The Normative Model of the Equitable Word” (Aljazairy, 2026b) and “Organisational Management in the Stage of Empowerment” (Aljazairy, 2026c) represent applied extensions within the same research project; the present study complements them by focusing specifically on leadership failure in crisis management.

The selection of Qur'anic verses is subject to a set of methodological controls to ensure objectivity and minimise bias. The scope is confined to verses in Sūrat Yūsuf relating to the King's model, and to verses connected with the story of Moses (PBUH) and Pharaoh across multiple surahs — al-A'rāf, Tā Hā, Yūnus, and al-Naml. The analytical unit is the leadership situation derived from the verses, classified under five main themes: decision-making;

consultation and listening; resource management and planning; crisis response; and the relationship between power and the public interest.

The analysis proceeds through several sequential stages: textual induction of selected verses; semantic and contextual analysis drawing on authoritative exegetical works to control meanings and prevent selective interpretation; conceptual classification; comparative analysis between the two models to reveal fundamental structural differences; and, finally, connecting findings to modern management concepts. The study adheres to the principle of limiting generalisation, whereby findings are understood within the boundaries of the Qur’anic context under study rather than extended in absolute terms.

6. Analysis and Comparison in Light of the Analytical Framework

6.1 Summary Comparison

Comparison Element	The King — Sound Management	Pharaoh — Failed Management
Cognitive Flexibility	High: transcends ideological constraints; explicitly admits inability	Very low: rigid even when certain of the truth
Information Openness	Open: consults experts; listens to a prisoner	Closed: ignores any dissenting opinion, even from his own officials
Institutional Delegation	Clear: delegates full authority to Joseph (PBUH)	Nonexistent: monopolises decision-making; declares himself a god
De-escalation Management	Successful: early intervention; proactive plan preceding the crisis	Failed: every decision worsens the crisis (escalation of commitment)
Emotional Intelligence	High: manages his ego; prioritises public interest	Zero: drowned in narcissism until destruction

6.2 Detailed Analysis of Each Element

6.2.1 Cognitive Flexibility

The King’s cognitive flexibility is manifested in his explicit admission of his inability to interpret the dream (Qur’ān 12:43) and his readiness to accept Joseph’s (PBUH) interpretation despite Joseph being a foreign prisoner. Aljazairy (2026a) noted that the Egyptian state of that period was a “theocratic-bureaucratic state centred on the divine authority of the ruler,” which makes the King’s willingness to listen to a prisoner from the common people an exceptional decision that broke established protocol and transcended the rigid hierarchical barrier (p. 98). This is precisely what distinguishes a sound leader: the ability to break institutional constraints when public interest demands it.

This behavioural shift constitutes a practical example of what modern management theory calls Situational Leadership — the leader’s ability to adjust their style according to the demands of the situation rather than adhering to a fixed pattern regardless of context (Hersey & Blanchard, 1969, p. 28).

In contrast, Pharaoh embodied cognitive rigidity. His obstinacy reached its peak when certainty of the truth provided no deterrent; God says: “And they rejected them, though their

souls acknowledged them with certainty, out of injustice and arrogance. So see how was the end of the corrupters” (Qur’ān 27:14). This verse makes clear that Pharaoh and his people were not in doubt about the truth of Moses (PBUH), but arrogance stood between them and sound judgement — and this is the essence of leadership failure: not born of ignorance but of the deliberate rejection of truth.

6.2.2 Information Openness

Listening to others’ opinions and engaging honestly with administrative reality is the first step in any sound crisis management. The King did not allow his pride to obstruct his search for the dream’s interpretation from those with expertise. When Joseph’s (PBUH) opinion reached him, he did not use Joseph’s prisoner status or foreign origin as a pretext but treated the counsel on its merit. Rahim (2002) designates this kind of management the “integrative style” — searching for a solution that serves all parties through openness to information (p. 80).

In contrast, Pharaoh displayed the phenomenon of “leadership deafness”: he did not attend to the arguments and proofs presented by Moses (PBUH) but persisted in his stubbornness despite accumulating evidence. Aljazairy (2026a) noted that “the ability to engage in genuine dialogue with others and to accept negative information about oneself is among the most prominent characteristics of the strategic leader” (p. 121).

6.2.3 Institutional Delegation

Delegating authority to competent individuals is one of the most prominent features of sound management in the King’s model: he did not hesitate to grant Joseph (PBUH) full executive powers. This is what modern management theory calls Distributed Leadership — distributing leadership tasks among more than one person according to competencies, increasing institutional effectiveness and crisis-response capacity (Drucker, 1954, p. 145).

Aljazairy (2026a) employed this same concept in his analysis of the Moses and Aaron (PBUT) model, noting that “the distribution of tasks, authority, and powers played an important and significant role in dealing with the risks of real-world conditions” (p. 129). What applies to Moses and Aaron (PBUT) applies in principle to the King and Joseph (PBUH): both models embody the integrative leadership dyad built on specialisation and division of roles.

Pharaoh, by contrast, insisted on monopolising decision-making and rejected any form of partnership. This centralisation was not merely an administrative style; it was organically linked to his theocratic identity, whose entire legitimacy rested on the notion that he was the living god on earth. Accepting another’s opinion therefore meant — in his own perspective — undermining that legitimacy.

6.2.4 De-escalation Management vs. Escalation of Commitment

Contemporary crisis management theories emphasise the importance of early intervention before the crisis reaches its peak. Lederach (1997) states that “conflict, when it escalates to a confrontational level, becomes more costly and difficult to contain” (p. 100). The King applied this principle by addressing the economic threat during its early planning phase, before the crisis erupted. Pharaoh, on the other hand, consistently pushed his crisis toward escalation rather than containment. He remained stubborn to the last moment, following his own desires even when wrong — ending with himself, his army, and his followers perishing.

What is particularly noteworthy here is the “escalation of commitment trap”: the tendency of leaders to persist on a failing course of action due to the psychological and political capital already invested in it, even as evidence of failure accumulates (Staw, 1981, p. 577). Every

time losses mounted before Pharaoh, the more he stiffened his position in defence of his false divine image.

6.2.5 Emotional Intelligence

The King, who possessed the absolute authority to refuse, chose instead to listen and delegate. His decision did not rest on social tradition, doctrinal obligation, or agreed-upon protocol in ancient Egypt, but came from the principle of impartiality and prioritising the state's interest over formal considerations. Aljazairy (2026a) described this as “the transition from closed theocratic leadership to sound technocratic leadership” (p. 103).

Pharaoh, facing an existential challenge, chose stubbornness and ruin. Aljazairy (2026a) examined the nature of this state in careful detail, noting that the Pharaonic state was “a closed military-theocratic state where despotism had reached the point of deifying the ruler, emptying institutions of their content, and directing law toward repression” (p. 168). Within this rigid structure, no decision could emerge that transcended the ruler's desires. The fundamental difference between the two leaders lies not in circumstance but in the internal disposition of each.

This analysis is consistent with Goleman's (1998) affirmation that leaders lacking self-awareness and impulse control are most prone to catastrophic decisions in times of crisis (p. 94). The King's model exhibits the self-awareness that enabled him to transcend his ego, while Pharaoh embodies emotional impulsivity that transformed every manageable crisis into an existential catastrophe.

6.3 Summary of Section 6

The comparison between the two models reveals that leadership failure in crisis management is not the result of weak resources or deficient information; it is in most cases the product of a defective internal structure within the leader. The primary components of that defective structure are: arrogance, dogmatism, the subordination of public interest to self-interest, and the refusal of consultation. Conversely, the foremost components of a sound leader's internal structure are: readiness to listen, cognitive flexibility, and the consistent prioritisation of institutional interest above all else.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

In light of the five-element analytical framework (cognitive flexibility, information openness, institutional delegation, de-escalation management, and emotional intelligence), the analysis confirms that the King's success was not mere chance but the product of high cognitive flexibility, openness to information that transcended class barriers, clear institutional delegation, successful de-escalation management, and emotional intelligence expressed in the prioritisation of state interest over personal interest. Pharaoh's failure, by contrast, was the inevitable result of cognitive rigidity reaching the point of denial even when certain of the truth, complete informational closure, total centralisation of power, escalation of commitment that drove his army to drowning, and an absence of emotional intelligence manifested in pathological narcissism.

This study examines two opposing Qur'anic models, revealing the profound administrative dimensions embedded in each. The research concludes that leadership failure in crisis

management cannot be explained by external factors alone; its real roots lie in the leader's internal disposition. Pharaoh's model embodies this failure in its most complete form, while the King's model offers a lesson in transforming crisis into an opportunity for reform and renewal.

Consistent with the methodology established by Aljazairy (2026a) in his analysis of the models of Joseph and Moses (PBUT), the study affirms that the Qur'anic narrative carries live, practical models for management and state-building that transcend the homiletic dimension to form an integrated conceptual system applicable to contemporary institutional reality. Furthermore, Aljazairy (2026b) points to a complete Qur'anic discursive structure for managing difference and preventing escalation — a framework that intersects with the present study's conclusion regarding the importance of placing a shared and just reference above individual interests.

The study has shown that leadership success depends not on possessing authority but on the capacity to deploy that authority in service of the institution, delegating to competent people, and remaining receptive to constructive criticism (Aljazairy, 2026c, pp. 15–16). The five elements of the analytical framework are not only suitable for interpreting the two Qur'anic models; they represent a diagnostic criterion applicable to evaluating leadership performance in any contemporary institutional context — thereby enhancing the value of the Qur'anic narrative as a living cognitive source for building management models that combine authenticity with scientific rigour.

7.2 Recommendations

Research Recommendations

1. Encourage interdisciplinary studies connecting the Qur'anic narrative to management sciences and crisis management.
2. Conduct comparative studies between the King's model in managing the famine crisis and other Qur'anic leadership models such as David and Solomon (PBUT).
3. Develop measurable indicators for the phenomenon of “structural leadership failure” derived from Qur'anic models.

Practical Recommendations

1. Adopt the principle of “delegating competence over hierarchy” in institutional decision-making structures, especially during crises.
2. Build an institutional culture that rewards listening and flexibility while holding leadership deafness and dogmatism to account.
3. Introduce formal mechanisms for managing crises in their early stages, inspired by the principle of prevention embodied in the King's Qur'anic model.

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